

TETRAHYMENA THERMOPHILA CU427/CU428

TETRAHYMENA THERMOPHILA CU427/28
T AND A BINARY STRETCHES

P.8802

T T T T T A A A T T T A A A A A A - 8818

↑1 ↑7 ↑2 ↑7
↓ ↓ ↓ ↓

P.8834

A A A A A A A A A T A T A A A T T T A A T - 8854

↑4 ↑6 ↑7 ↑2 ↑7 ↑6
↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓

P.7940

A A A A A A A T T A A A A T T A T T A A A T A A A A A A A - 7967

↑4 ↑2 ↑7 ↑2 ↑5 ↑1 ↑7 ↑6 ↑4
↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓

P.5448

A A A A A A T A A A A T T T A - 5462

↑4 ↑6 ↑4 ↑2 ↑7
↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓

P.7971

78024

T A A T T A C A C A C A C A C A C A C A C A C A T A C A T

TETRAHYMENA THERMOPHILA CU 427/28-T AND A BINARY STRETCHES (EXCEPT 7971-7802)

TETRAHYMENA THERMOPHILA CU427/CU428 - TAND A BINARY STRETCHES

P. 8592

T A A T T T T A T T T T A A A A A T A T T T T T T T T T A →

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→ A A T A A A T T T T A A • P. 8635

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⇒

P. 8635

P. 5710

P. 5726

→ A A T A A A A A T A A T A A A A A • P. 5726

P. 8773

P. 8791

→ T T A T T T T T T T A A T A A A A A A • P. 2791

P. 2238

AAA, ATT, TAA, TTT, AATA, AATA, AATA, AAA →

↓

→ TAA, AATA, ATT, ATTT, AA°

↓

↓

↓

P. 2284

P. 8224

P. 8236

→ AAA, AATA, TATA, TATA, TATA°

P. 8751

→ AAA, ATTT, TTT, TAA, AATTT, TTTT° P. 8770

↓

P. 8770

P. 8802

P. 8818

→ TTT, TTA, AA, TTT, AAA, AA° P. 8818

P.5329

→ T A A, T T T, T T T, T A A, A A A, T T T T T T A A A A A A T T T - P.5359

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⇓

⇓

→ A T T T, T T T T, T A, T T T, A T T A T A A A A A P.8876

P.2672

→ T T A, T T A, T T T, A A T, A T T T T T A T T T A A T T T A A T A - P.2708

P.2708

P.5352

P.8856

P.8876

P.2708

Unary operators could be defined on the sets of three and four elements as presented below and their detailed applications on DNA are possible to find at www.visualdna.org

Let Q_3 be a set of three elements a, b and c : $Q_3 \{a, b, c\}$. Within this three-element set we can define unary operator u_3 which transforms each element of this set into itself or another element of the same set. This unary operator (u_3) is defined by 27 operations. With these 27 operations we could generate 81 basic strands out of which 33 are different, three of them trivial (no change). These 33 strands we will consider to be basic for the three-element set Q_3 , and we will assign one number from 1 to 33 for each basic strand. Thus we will consolidate all the operations that generate identical strands with given first element, into one operation that generates that particular strand. We will now define a set of four elements Q_4 with elements a, b, c and d : $Q_4 \{a, b, c, d\}$. These four elements are selected to correspond to the visual representation of the four bases of DNA (C, A, G, T). Within this set we will define unary operator u_4 represented by 256 operations. With these 256 operations we could generate 1024 basic strands out of which only 196 are different, four of them being trivial. We could consolidate all operations that generate identical strands with given first element (starting point), and assign to each of them a number from 1 to 196. These basic four-element strands could be then represented as 196 corresponding D-icons. And in case of four-element set, we could generate complex strands with successive application of two or more different unary operations.

